

Observations on the black-faced huntsman spider *Olios correvoni nigrifrons* Lawrence, 1928 from Southern Africa (Araneae: Sparassidae)

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ABSTRACT: *Olios correvoni* Lessert, 1921 is an African endemic species described from Tanzania and the subspecies *Olios correvoni nigrifrons* was described by Lawrence, 1928 from Namibia. The subspecies is also known from South Africa and Botswana. It is a nocturnal spider that wanders at night searching for prey. During the day, they are found in silk retreats made in different microhabitats. Observations on their general morphology, behaviour, and distribution with photographs of live specimens are provided.

Keywords: biodiversity, conservation biogeography, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

Several *Olios* species were sampled during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). *Olios* Walckenaer, 1837 is known for 164 species and two subspecies (World Spider Catalog, 2024) and recorded from Africa, southern Europe, and Asia. The genus was revised by Jäger (2020) who recognized eight species groups and only 87 species. According to him many species are misplaced.

Olios correvoni Lessert, 1921 described from Tanzania was recognized by Jäger (2020). Two subspecies *O. correvoni choupangensis* Lessert, 1936 from Mozambique and *O. correvoni nigrifrons* Lawrence, 1928 from Namibia are listed in the World Spider Catalog (2024) but not mentioned by Jäger (2020).

Lawrence (1928) description of *O. correvoni nigrifrons* from a single female. However, several specimens were sampled during SANSa surveys corresponding to the description of the subspecies. Observations on their general morphology, behaviour, and distribution in Southern Africa with photographs of live specimens are provided here.

TAXONOMY

Olios correvoni nigrifrons Lawrence, 1928

Olios correvoni nigrifrons Lawrence, 1928: 249 (f); Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022: 19.

Descriptive characters: Female: TL 13–15 mm. Carapace fawn and bordered anteriorly by a transverse dark band covering the anterior row of eyes and part of the clypeus (Figs 1–2); carapace with dense white setae around the posterior eye row and occasionally with scattered spots (Fig. 4); chelicerae are black, bearing dark setae. Eyes are in two rows with the anterior row straight; anterior median eyes are less than their diameter apart and larger than the laterals; the posterior row is slightly procurved, with medians more than twice their diameter apart; posterior medians are distinctly smaller than anterior medians. Abdomen long oval; yellowish with median pale brown heart mark (Figs 4–5); some specimens pale with no distinct pattern, only occasionally with scattered grey setae; venter uniformly pale. Legs are the same colour as the carapace, with scattered faint spots; tarsi and metatarsi of I, II, and III, IV with dense slate-grey scopula; sometimes femur also with scattered scopula (Fig. 3). Epigyne as in Figs 6–7. Male unknown.

Figures 1–3. *Olios correvoni nigrifrons* female. 1. Female in an old *Stegodyphus* retreat in Namibia (A. Eichhoff). 2. Female with egg sac from retreat under a stone from Paulshoek (R. Christiaan) 3. Female dorsal view from Namibia (A. Eichhoff).

Figures 4–7. *Olios correvoni nigrifrons* female. 4. Dorsal view, alcohol specimen. 5. Dorsal view life specimen. 6–7. Epigyne. Credits: 4 & 6. ASD. 5., Anka Eichhoff. 7. After Lawrence (1928).

METHODS

Voucher specimens sampled ($n=26$) collected during SANSA surveys are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council (ARC) in Pretoria. SANSA requested photographs of spiders for the SANSA Virtual Museum (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012), and several photographs of the species were received from the public.

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Eswatini, **Botswana:** Okwa River (-22.43, 22.96); Kuke Pan (-22.00, 22.00); Molepolole (-24.40, 25.49).

Namibia: Farm Otjitambi (-19.48, 15.11); Farm Vergenoeg (-21.10, 18.18) and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA (Fig. 8): **Eastern Cape:** Breakfast Vlei, above Kwancukunca stream (-33.08, 26.95); Middelburg (-31.49, 24.99); Mkambati Nature Reserve (31.31; 29.97). **Free State:** Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68); Bloemfontein (Farm Deelhoek) (-29.11, 26.22); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.50, 26.80); Luckhoff (-29.73, 24.77); Koppiesdam Nature Reserve (-27.13, 27.42); Willem Pretorius Nature Reserve (-28.17, 27.12). **Gauteng:** Pretoria/Tshwane: Brooklyn (-25.77, 28.24); Moreleta Park (-25.81, 28.29); Barberspan (-26.62, 25.58). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Bonamanzi Nature Reserve (-28.02, 32.28); Ithala Nature Reserve (Doornkraal Camp) (-27.51, 31.23); Ndumo Game Reserve (Crocodile Farm) (-26.87, 32.24); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Sodwana Bay National Park (Forest Station) (-27.4, 32.76); Hluhluwe (-28.02, 32.28). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Lajuma Mountain Retreat (-23.03, 29.45); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.95, 29.87); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park (Skukuza Camp) (-25.00, 31.97); Kruger National Park Pretoriuskop (-25.140, 31.208). **North West:** Barberspan (-26.62, 25.58); Swartbooisdrift, Black Rock (-25.27, 28.13). **Northern Cape:** Augrabies National Park (-28.53, 20.29); Namaqua National Park (-30.05, 17.35); Tswalu Game Reserve (-27.30, 22.44); Paulshoek, Kamiesberg (-30.366, 18.256). **Western Cape:** Botrivier (-34.21, 19.2); Prince Albert (Tierberg) (-33.22, 22.03).

Figure 8. Known distribution in South Africa. Credit: S. Foord

Figures 9–13. *Olios correvoni nigrifrons*. 9–10. Female with egg sac in silk retreat at Paulshoek (R. Christiaan). 11. Female in old spider nest. 12. Between plants. 13. From rolled up leaf (11–13. A. Eichhoff)

CONSERVATION

The subspecies, is known from several southern African countries. As part of SANSA it has been sampled from all the nine provinces of South Africa and is included in several checklists: Mkambati Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2011); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (Fouche *et al.*, 2013); Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2019); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2009); Tswalu Game Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2018); Augrabies National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021); Prince Albert, Tierberg (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022) and Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006).

Although it is presently known only from one sex due to its vast geographical range, the subspecies is listed as being of least concern. When the African *Olios* fauna is revised, this subspecies will probably be recognized as a valid species.

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